

In-situ Composite Manufacture using an Electrostatic Spray Process and Filament Winding

Mark Duvall, Karthik Ramani
School of Mechanical Engineering
Purdue University

ABSTRACT

Manufacture of thermoplastic composites is expensive due to the use of pre-impregnated materials. Powder processing shows promise as an impregnation technique for a cost-effective manufacturing process. The overall objective of this study is to develop a continuous process for impregnating and consolidating thermoplastic composites using powder polymers in a filament winding process. A negative corona electrostatic spray gun is used to charge and direct the powder to adhere to both sides of a spread fiber tow. The tows are then pulled through ceramic heaters to coat the fibers, and then consolidated via filament winding using hot nitrogen gas heaters.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are enjoying a steady and significant increase in popularity across many different products and industries. In particular, thermoplastic matrix composites are drawing increased interest, in part due to their excellent toughness, impact and chemical resistance, and potential for shorter processing times when compared with their thermoset counterparts. Unfortunately, the high melt viscosities of thermoplastic polymers hinder the uniform impregnation of the fiber with resin during component manufacture. For thermoplastic composite materials to expand beyond their current high performance and niche markets, cost-effective processes must be developed that rapidly and uniformly impregnate fibers with resin, and then consolidate them at high speeds into finished components.

A process currently under development at Purdue University has proven effective for impregnating continuous glass or carbon fibers with a variety of different thermoplastic polymer powders. This technique uses an electrostatic powder spray gun to charge and deposit polymer powders onto a continuous fiber tow. This method has the advantage of combining the mechanical entrapment of the powder with electrostatic effects [1,2]. The resulting flexible composite "towpreg" from the spray process can then be used for a variety of component manufacture techniques, including compression molding, pultrusion, braiding, and filament winding. This paper discusses the electrostatic spray process and its use in tandem with an on-line consolidation apparatus for filament winding. Together, the two processes comprise an in-situ composite component manufacturing line. This combined

process is used to spray coat glass fibers with PEKK (poly(aryl) ether ketone ketone) powder and then manufacture cylinders in-situ with the resulting towpreg material.

THERMOPLASTIC POWDER IMPREGNATION

Different techniques of impregnation have been used for manufacturing thermoplastic composites. These include melt impregnation, fiber co-mingling, film stacking, solution processing, and powder impregnation. Among these techniques, powder processing is emerging as an attractive method for achieving a low-cost manufacturing process. A review of some commercial powder processes is provided by Fisher [3]. Iyer and Drzal [4] discuss some issues involved in powder processing of thermoplastic composites. Powder processes may be classified as either wet or dry. In wet powder techniques, the fibers are pulled through a liquid medium in which the polymer powder is suspended in a slurry (Ramani, et al. [5]). Dry powder processes impregnate the fibers directly with the polymeric powder.

Dry powder processes may be distinguished by the method used to deposit the powder on the fiber tow. Most dry powder processes rely on either mechanical entrapment or electrostatic attraction of the powder to the tow. A vast majority of the work using dry powders has used carbon fibers for reinforcement. Carbon fiber tows are easily exposed through spreading as they typically do not have a significant amount of binder that holds the individual filaments together. Muzzy and Varughese [6,7] developed and commercialized a process which uses an electrostatic fluidized bed to coat the fibers, producing a flexible tow-preg. Other efforts include Baucom and Marchello [8] with an electrostatic fluidized bed, Throne and Sohn [9] with an electrostatic spray gun to create a charged powder cloud in an enclosure for coating carbon fibers, and Iyer [10] using acoustic energy to suspend powder particles in a vertical tube.

FILAMENT WINDING

Filament winding is a common method developed for manufacturing cylindrical and curvilinear components from thermoset composites. With the addition of heat and pressure sources for consolidation, filament winders can also use thermoplastic composites. Three forms of heating dominate current research on thermoplastic filament winding: laser (Beyeler and Gucer [11]), hot gas (Carpenter [12] and Cirino [13]), and focused infra-red radiation (Whiting [14]). A compaction roller provides pressure on the incoming tow as it is heated, bonding it to the existing composite substrate in a continuous process. A commercially viable filament winding process should combine high speed processing with quality, low-void parts that do not require costly post-processing.

The most common material forms for thermoplastic filament winding are pre-consolidated tapes. This simplifies the winding process, as the fibers of most tapes are fully impregnated in the thermoplastic matrix. Winding a partially consolidated material like the coated spray process tows is inherently more difficult, as the polymer matrix must be melted and impregnated into the fibers during the winding process. The effects of material type on the final quality of filament wound thermoplastic composites are discussed by Colton and Leach [15]. Lauke and Friedrich discuss in better detail the consolidation of a powder prepreg material similar to the coated tows produced by the electrostatic spray process [16].

PROCESS DESCRIPTION

A diagram of the entire electrostatic spray impregnation and filament winding process is shown in Figure 1. At the payout end of the process, a fiber creel is mounted on a bi-directional fiber tensioner to maintain an even line tension. The fiber then passes through a spreading area where the tow is spread to expose the individual fibers and the entire tow is moistened with water to enable electrical conductivity for electrostatic deposition. Immediately after spreading, the tow passes underneath a negative corona electrostatic powder spray gun, which charges and deposits the thermoplastic powder upon the tow. The powder coated fiber tow then passes through a simple flat ceramic heater that melts the powder, adhering the polymer to the fibers and resulting in the finished electrostatic spray-coated composite towpreg.

After leaving the ceramic heater, the spray-coated composite towpreg enters the on-line filament winding apparatus. A clockwise-rotating steel mandrel takes up the fiber tow produced from the electrostatic spray area, and provides the surface for consolidating the coated towpreg into a finished cylinder. A ceramic guide centers the coated tow underneath a polished stainless steel compression roller. An air cylinder applies and regulates the consolidation force of the roller. At the nip point, or point of consolidation between the incoming tow and the existing composite substrate, a fast-response, hot nitrogen gas heater melts the thermoplastic polymer, facilitating the consolidation to the substrate, and also the wetting out of any remaining dry fibers in the incoming tow.

Fiber Spreading

Spreading the fibers before spraying on the polymer improves deposition in several ways. By spreading the tow to expose the individual fibers, the powder can impregnate through the thickness of the tow more thoroughly. Also, with more surface area to deposit charged polymer onto, the maximum achievable resin volume fraction increases. This is important when manufacturing towpreg for applications such as braiding, which may require a higher resin content. Proper fiber spreading results in a relatively wide and thin towpreg with good flexibility. Most pre-impregnated thermoplastic tapes have limited flexibility and drape, which can further limit their versatility.

Fiber spreading technique depends upon the type of fibers used. Fiberglass is typically difficult to spread as the individual fibers tend to be bound tightly together by the sizing. Before spreading, the fiberglass tow is transiently heated by a nitrogen gas heater. This heater softens the polymer binder on the tow while the nitrogen gas helps reduce or prevent degradation of the sizing while the gas flow helps separate the tow into individual filaments. After heating, a fine water mist is sprayed onto the tow to provide electrical conductivity for the electrostatic deposition.

The tow is spread mechanically by a "geodesic fiber spreader" to between four and six times its original width. As the tow enters the spreading stage, a pulley positions the tow laterally and constrains it to pass over a smooth, polished disk. The existing fiber tension pulls the filament against both the curved leading and trailing edges of the disk. Each individual fiber of the tow will seek the shortest path across the disk, causing the tow to spread over the angled surface of the disk. A number of factors help determine the final spreading width, including fiber tension, angle of the spreading disk, relative position of the disk and pulley, tow preheat, and amount of water added.

Electrostatic Powder Spray Deposition

The electrostatic powder spray process consists of powder being pneumatically conveyed from a fluidization chamber to a spray gun. The gun nozzle contains a pointed electrode which is maintained at a high negative voltage (-30 to -100 kilovolts) to create a corona discharge at the electrode. The ions produced in the corona region charge the powder. The charged powder is then directed towards the grounded fibers under the influence of aerodynamic, electrostatic, and gravitational forces.

$$F_{net} = F_a + F_g + F_e$$

A very thorough review of charging and deposition of powder coatings is presented by Wu [17]. Ang and Lloyd [18] studied particle trajectories from an electrostatic spray gun. The aerodynamic force is responsible for particle transport from the gun. The charged polymeric particles, placed in the electric field between the corona and the grounded fibers, experience a force that directs them towards the fiber tow. In addition, the charged particles themselves create a space charge, that results in the particles "fanning out" when exiting from the nozzle. However the space charge is significant only in the region near the nozzle. When the particles are within a few millimeters of the fiber tow, the image field between the particles and the fiber, results in the final deposition on the tow. The net electric field is the vector sum of the space charge field due to the charged particles and ions, the applied field generated by the corona electrode, the image field, and the field resulting from the deposited layer of charge particles on the grounded substrate.

$$E_{net} = E_{space} + E_{electrode} + E_{image} + E_{deposited}$$

PROCESS CHARACTERISTICS

PEKK powder supplied by Dupont with a volume average diameter of 72 microns were used in the experiments. The fibers used were Owens-Corning Type-30 E-glass rovings with an experimental sizing chemistry, average fiber diameter of 16 microns, and a yield of 450 yards/pound. The position and orientation of the gun in the experiments is shown in Figure 3. For this series of experiments, the standard parameters are a corona voltage of -85 kV, air flow pressure of 13.8 kPa, nitrogen exit temperature of 750°C and flow rate of 2.55 m³/hr, heater temperature of 500°C, fiber tension and velocity of 200 grams and 25.4 mm/sec, and a fluidizing pressure of 41.4 kPa.

Static Fiber Tow Experiment

The effect of the corona voltage of the gun on powder deposition was explored by spraying onto a stationary fiber tow for 15 seconds. After deposition, the fiber tow was pulled at very low speed through an oven to melt and adhere the powder to the tow. The coated tow was cut into 13 millimeter long segments and weighed to determine the resin distribution along the fiber tow. Figure 4 shows the powder deposition along the length of the tow, with and without the corona voltage applied to the gun. The electric field strength is strongest at the nozzle exit region, as shown by region "A" in Figure 2. In this region, the powder is strongly directed to the tow by the electrostatic forces. Uncharged powder is influenced only by the air flow and gravity, and deposits on the fibers only through direct interception with the spread fiber tow. It can be seen from Figure 4 that half the total deposition occurs within a distance of 25 millimeters from the nozzle exit *with* corona voltage and within a distance of 65 millimeters from the nozzle exit *without* corona voltage. Clearly, the electrostatic forces cause more powder deposition on the fibers near the nozzle exit.

Powder Deposition versus Air Flow

The delivery system that supplies the powder the electrostatic spray gun consists of a fluidizing hopper and a powder pump. An applied air pressure to the spray gun first flows through a venturi in the powder pump, drawing the fluidized particles up from the hopper and entraining them in the air flow. Between air pressures of 6.9 and 20.7 kilopascals, this relationship between air pressure and mass flow rate of powder from the hopper is

$$\dot{m} = 0.028 P_{flow} + 0.030$$

The fluidizing pressure in the hopper does not significantly affect the powder mass flow rate. The amount of powder deposited onto an unspread fiber tow was measured as a function of the applied air pressure to the powder pump. The air pressure was varied from 7.0 to 21.0 kilopascals. The amount of powder deposited onto fibers was found by measuring a twelve inch sample of coated glass fibers. The resin weight fraction was averaged for three samples at each pressure setting and is shown in Figure 5.

As the powder mass flowrate increases, the powder deposition achieves a maximum for every orientation of the gun. For the configuration shown in Figure 3, the maximum deposition occurs at 14 kilopascals, as shown in Figure 5. Further increase in the powder mass flowrate increases the exit velocities of the powder and air. High powder velocities overcome the electrostatic image force near the fiber tow while a high air velocity removes powder that is already deposited on the fibers. These factors contribute to a reduction in powder deposition.

Powder Deposition versus Corona Voltage

The amount of powder deposited onto an unspread fiber tow is shown as a function of the applied corona voltage in Figure 6. The corona voltage was varied from -40 to -100 kV in 15 kV increments. As shown in Figure 6, powder deposition increases until it saturates at a corona voltage of -70 kV. Initial increase of the corona voltage (-40 to -70 kV) causes a higher charge per particle as well as a stronger applied electric field. These two effects result in higher electrostatic forces, which directs the powder to the fibers, in the nozzle exit region (region "A", Figure 2). However, increasing the corona voltage results in greater ion generation from the corona region. Once the particles achieve their charge saturation limit, the increased ion generation contributes solely to the space charge density. The space charge effect counteracts the increase in electric field strength obtained by the higher corona voltage. Also, the image force, which is proportional to the square of the particle charge, reaches its maximum when the charge saturation limit is achieved. Therefore, once the particles reach their charge saturation limit, there is no significant increase in the image force or net electrostatic force to improve deposition.

Powder Deposition versus Fiber Velocity

The amount of powder deposited onto a spread fiber tow as a function of the fiber tow velocity and electrostatic gun height was monitored. The fiber velocity varied between 13 and 51 millimeters per second while the gun nozzle was positioned 13 and 38 millimeters above the fiber tow. Figure 7 shows the powder deposition as a function of fiber velocity for both the low (LO) and high (HI) gun positions, *with* (WE) and *without* (WOE) electrostatics (corona voltage) applied. Powder deposition decreases at higher fiber velocities and increases with electrostatics. Without electrostatics, the uncharged powder falls off due to the vibration of the moving fiber tow. When the gun is closer to the fiber tow, the electric field intensity is greater resulting in strong electrostatic forces directing the particles to the fiber tow. Hence, a lower position of the gun with electrostatics is beneficial for good deposition and adherence of the powder.

IN-SITU FILAMENT WINDING

This operation demonstrates the impregnation and consolidation of electrostatic spray coated tow in a single continuous process. An apparatus to perform on-line consolidation during the winding of the coated tows onto a standard commercial filament winder was designed. The device uses opposing steel rollers mounted on identical air cylinders (Figure 8). This design allows the support rollers of the one air cylinder to counteract the force generated by the consolidation roller. This consolidation unit can function as an add-on component to a commercial filament winder. Many of the machines are designed exclusively for thermoset composite winding, which typically does not employ large

consolidation forces. With this design, the consolidation forces are contained within the frame of the unit, and are not transmitted to the frame of the winding machine itself. This also allows for the manufacture of smaller diameter tubes without causing undue deflection in the mandrel during winding.

The coated tows from the spray process consist of a polymer sheath encapsulating a fiber bundle. The winding process must complete the impregnation and consolidation to produce a quality, low-void part. Hot nitrogen gas heaters were used for pre-heating and final heating of the tows before consolidation. As the coated tow winds beneath the consolidation roller, the polymer sheath is molten and the fiber bundle is about 7-15 fibers thick (Figure 9). The pressure from the roller flattens the tow and increases the width of the tow as much as 30%. This reduces the thickness of the fiber bundle and forces the molten polymer sheath on either side of the bundle inward.

Microstructure analysis of the tows revealed that the further impregnation occurred through the thickness of the tow during the consolidation. Optical micrographs of the consolidated cylinders (Figure 10) reveal good consolidation and minimal void content. The coated tows used consisted of 60% glass fibers by weight. The microstructure of the manufactured parts is relatively free of ordered resin-rich and fiber-rich areas. The presence of these regions is common in filament winding and indicates that the consolidation process does not effectively distribute the resin, leaving thick polymer borders between tape or towpreg layers.

CONCLUSIONS

An electrostatic spray impregnation process which combines the benefits of both mechanical entrapment and electrostatic adhesion of the powder has been developed for the coating of continuous fibers. The electrostatic field due to the corona voltage is used to coat both sides of the spread fiber tow. This spray process can produce coated towpreg with uniform resin volume fractions up to 70% by controlling gun air flow, corona voltage, tow speed, and gun position. The resulting highly flexible material form is useful for numerous methods of component manufacture such as filament winding, pultrusion, braiding and compression molding. A consolidation device using opposing compression rollers and hot gas heating was designed to investigate the manufacture of the spray process towpreg into filament wound cylinders in a complete in-situ impregnation and consolidation process.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank Nordson Corporation for their donation of all of the electrostatic powder spray equipment used in this process. The support of National Science Foundation Grant DDM-9308498 is greatly appreciated. Rick Caillat and Mark Bays are thanked for their help on the filament winding. Donation of the PEKK powder from DuPont and glass fibers from Owens Corning Fiberglas is also appreciated. Finally we would like to thank Dan Woolard for his continued advice.

REFERENCES

1. K. Ramani and D. E. Woolard, Invention Disclosure #93036, Office of Technology Transfer, Purdue University (1993).
2. K. Ramani, D.E. Woolard, and M. S. Duvall, *An Electrostatic Powder Spray Process for*

Manufacturing Thermoplastic Composites, Processing, Design, and Performance of Composite Materials, ASME Winter Annual Meeting, Chicago, Nov 13-19, 1994.

3. K. J. Fisher, *Adv. Compos.*, **8**, 30 (1993).
4. S. R. Iyer and L. T. Drzal, *J. Thermoplastic Compos. Mater.*, **3**, 325 (1990).
5. K. Ramani, M. Tryfonidis, C. Hoyle, and J. Gentry, Processing, Fabrication, and manufacturing of Composite Materials, ASME MD-Volume **35**, 115 (1992).
6. J. D. Muzzy and B. Varughese, U.S. Patent No. 5094883, (1992).
7. J. D. Muzzy and B. Varughese, U.S. Patent No. 5171630, (1992).
8. R. M. Baucom and J. M. Marchello, NASA Technical Memorandum 102648, (1992).
9. J. L. Throne and M. Sohn, *Proc. 35th Int'l. SAMPE Symp.*, **35**, 2086 (1990).
10. S. R. Iyer, L. T. Drzal, and K. Jayaraman, U.S. Patent No. 5102690, (1992).
11. E. Beyeler, W. Phillips, and S. Guceri, *J. of Thermoplastic Comp. Mat.*, **1**, 107, (1988)
12. C. Carpenter and J. Colton, *Proc. 38th Int'l SAMPE Symp.*, **38**, 205, (1993)
13. M. Cirino, T. Watson, and D.E. Hauber, *Proc. 36th Int'l SAMPE Symp.*, **36**, 2184, (1991)
14. J. Whiting, *3rd Int. Conf. on Autom. Comp.* **27**, 1, (1991)
15. J. Colton and D. Leach, *ANTEC '91 Conference Proc.*, (1991).
16. B. Lauke and K. Friedrich, *Composites Manufacturing*, Vol 4 No 2, (1993).
17. S. Wu, *Polym.-Plast. Technol. Eng.*, **7**, 119 (1976).
18. M.L. Ang and P.J. Lloyd. *Int. J. Multiphase Flow*, McGraw-Hill, London (1969).

Fig 1. Integrated process for in-situ coating and consolidation of thermoplastic composites

Fig 2. Side view of spray deposition area for parallel orientation of gun to fiber tow.

Fig 3. Gun position and fiber spreader

Fig 5. Deposition versus air flow pressure

Fig 7. Deposition versus fiber velocity

Fig 4. Static fiber tow deposition vs. distance

Fig 6. Deposition versus corona tip voltage

Fig 8. Consolidation unit for filament winder

Fig 9. Spray process tow prep cross-section

Fig 10. Filament wound tube cross-section